

Rainfall and discharge induced change in hydrodynamic of Tlawng River, Mizoram

DAVID A LALRAMCHULLOA^{1*}, PC LALRINDIKA², GABRIEL LALCHHANDAMA³,
LALRINTLUANGA⁴, LALRINPUII⁵

¹Department of Geography, Assistant Professor, Government J Thankima College, Aizawl, Mizoram
Corresponding Author

²Department of Geography, Assistant Professor, Government J Thankima College, Aizawl, Mizoram

³Department of Geography, Assistant Professor, Government J Thankima College, Aizawl, Mizoram

⁴Department of Geography, Assistant Professor, Government J Thankima College, Aizawl, Mizoram

⁵Department of Geography, Assistant Professor, Government J Thankima College, Aizawl, Mizoram

Abstract

Understanding the morpho-dynamics of the Tlawng River, with an emphasis on the interaction of rainfall, discharge, and river dynamics, is the main objective of this study. Across several stations along the river, the study examines the relationship between seasonal rainfall, river discharge, and channel shape. The river's flow rate, hydraulic geometry, and discharge variations have been measured in the lean and rainy seasons. A positive relationship has been observed between rainfall and river discharge, with larger discharge values observed downstream. Discharge patterns are also influenced by cross-sectional area, flow velocity, and channel dimensions and also the discharge rates significantly increased during the wet season in contrast to the lean season, indicating considerable seasonal fluctuations

Keywords: morpho-dynamics, discharge, hydraulic geometry, cross-sectional area, flow velocity, channel dimensions.

1. Introduction

As rivers are dynamic systems, they are influenced by a number of features, such as topography, sediment load in the system, confinement and discharge. The movement of water within a channel is called channel fluid dynamics and is crucial in shaping river morphology [1]. In the case of the Tlawng River, which begins in a youthful stage (upper course) with steep gradients and high velocities, channel dynamics are highly influenced by factors such as discharge, sediment transport, and hydraulic geometry. This study examines how rainfall impacts discharge, how discharge affects the river's velocity, and how these factors interplay to shape the river's morphology. River discharge is critical as it governs the speed of river flow and its erosive potential [6].

The flow of water inside a watercourse, extending from its source to its mouth, can be described as channel hydraulics [6]. This process is governed by factors like channel slope, width, surface roughness, and water volume. Rivers in their youthful stage typically possess a steeper gradient compared to those in the mature or old stage [8]. Since the upper reach of the Tlawng River falls within this youthful stage, its slope is considerably steeper than in the middle and lower sections [7]. Consequently, water moves at a higher average velocity of about 0.20 m/s in the upper course, resulting in the development of numerous erosional features along the channel. However, as roughness increases due to a thick bed load and sturdy rock formations along the riverbed and banks, the average velocity decreases to approximately 0.08 m/s [7] (Table 1).

River discharge plays a key role in determining flow velocity [6-8] Reaches with greater discharge carry larger water volumes and maintain less frictional contact with the riverbed, which results in higher flow speeds [11]. In the lower course, particularly around Bairabi, an increase in discharge corresponds with a rise in velocity, averaging about 0.33 m/s. The Tlawng River is not expected to undergo significant changes in its channel pattern in the near term, since its velocity remains relatively stable within a consistent and uniform channel.

Stations/Cross-sectional area	Velocity in m/s (Average)
Bairabi	0.31
Ailawng	0.08
Sairang	0.10
Lunglei	0.20

Table 1: Average velocity at selected cross-sectional area in Tlawng River.

2. Location and extent of study area

Tlawng is the lengthiest river in Mizoram, stretching about 320 km before meeting the Barak River at Katakhal in Assam [7] (Figure 1(a) & (b)). Of this total length, nearly 234 km lies within Mizoram. The river has its source in Zopui Hill, located roughly 8 km east of Lunglei town (22°51'North, 92°48'East), at an elevation of around 1,395 metres (4,576 feet) [10]. By the time it reaches Katakhal (24°49'N, 92°38' E), its altitude declines to approximately 17 metres (63 ft), where it eventually merges with the Barak. The catchment area of the Tlawng River basin covers approximately 5,846 km² [7].

Figure 1: (a) Location map of the study area & (b) Tlawng river course

3. Methodology

- (1) Float method has been employed to calculate the channel flow velocity. For measuring the depth and width of the river level staff and a tape measure is utilised.
- (2) The river discharge at chosen stations has been calculated Through Area Velocity Method [2].

$$Q = w \times d \times v$$

Here,

Q denotes stream discharge (m³/s), w, d, and v indicates channel width (m), average depth (m), and mean flow velocity (m/s) at the cross section, respectively.

- (3) SPSS has been employed to examine different hydraulic parameters.
- (4) The river channel was digitized from Survey of India toposheets using ASTER DEM image in ArcGIS10.5 software.

4. Results and discussion:

4.1 Hydraulic Geometry and Discharge Measurements

The discharge of a river plays a dominant role in shaping its hydraulic geometry [8]. Channel discharge denotes the amount of water moving through a specific cross-sectional area of the river within a given time frame [9]. Measurements of discharge may either be instantaneous, capturing flow at a particular moment or over a short duration, or continuous, which provide long-term records of flow variations [2]. At any location along the river, channel dimensions are primarily influenced by the upstream inflow delivered to that point [4]. In essence, it is the amount of water passing a defined section of the channel during a set of period. Near the river's source, the drainage area is relatively small and therefore contributes less

discharge, whereas downstream, both discharge and channel size normally increase in proportion to the catchment area. In this study, river discharge was calculated using the Area Velocity Method [2].

$$Q = w \times d \times v$$

Here, Q denotes stream discharge (m³/s), w, d, and v indicates channel width (m), average depth (m), and mean flow velocity (m/s) at the cross section, respectively. In general, for rivers with alluvial beds, both the average velocity and the width-to-depth ratio tend to upsurge downstream as discharge becomes larger [5].

River discharge data for PHE site, Dihmunzawl was obtained from the PHE Department, 2015 records (Table 2 & Table 3) (Figure 5). In all the other stations at Ailawng, Lunglei (Pukpui), Bairabi, and Sairang, river discharge observations were carried out at the site (Table 4, 5, 6, 7). In Ailawng, Bairabi and Sairang, measurements were taken from three separate stations in each town, while in Lunglei two stations were used. To analyze how seasonal changes in climate affect the river's behavior, discharge was recorded during both the dry season and the monsoon period.

Date/Month/Year	Discharge 'Q' in MLD (Million litres per day)	Remarks
1/03/2010	182.3	Area-velocity method
20/03/2010	127.01	
27/03/2010	125.28	
24/04/2010	224.64	Water level changes due to rainfall
Total	659.23	
8/02/2011	202.95	Area-velocity method
15/02/2011	187.17	
8/03/2011	174.53	
15/03/2011	173.66	After 15th March water level rises again due to rainfall
Total	738.31	
11/02/2012	123.43	Area-velocity method
17/02/2012	115	Discharge is lesser than preceding years
25/02/2012	76.5	Discharge upsurges after rainfall in the month of March
Total	314.93	
18/03/2013	132.72	Area-velocity method
23/03/2013	124	Average discharge recorded
28/03/2013	121.4	
Total	378.12	

Table 2: River discharge at PHE site Dihmunzawl adapted from PHE Department,2015

Year	Minimum river discharge in MLD	Difference
2010	125.28	
2011	173.66	-48.38
2012	76.5	97.16
2013	121.4	-44.9
2019	70.742	
2020	65.97	-4.77
2021	31.461	-34.51

Table 3: River discharge at PHE site Dihmunzawl adapted from PHE Department, 2015

Stations	Cross-Sectional Area (sqm)	Discharge (cumecs)	Million liters per day (MLD)
Station 1(6th Oct 2018)	34.2	1.035	89.4
Station 2 (6th Oct 2018)	10.54	0.695	60
Station 1 May 2018	25.7	8.8	760

Table 4: Water Volume at Lunglei station adapted from Lalramchulloa, 2021

Stations	Cross-Sectional Area (sqm)	Discharge (cumecs)	Million liters per day (MLD)
Station 1 (6 th Feb 2017)	10.41	1.8	155
Station 2 (6 th Feb 2017)	19.9	2.1	181
Station 3 (6 th Feb 2017)	28.64	2.5	216
Station 3 August 2017	118.7	17.8	1538

Table 5: Water Volume at Sairang station adapted from Lalramchulloa, 2021

Stations	Cross-Sectional Area (sqm)	Discharge (cumecs)	Million liters per day (MLD)
Station 1 (3 rd March 2017)	26.4	1.42	122
Station 2 (3 rd March 2017)	53.3	4.3	371
Station 3 (3 rd March 2017)	45.98	4.1	354
Station 2 Sept 2017	127.7	178.8	15646

Table 6: Water Volume at Ailawng station adapted from Lalramchulloa, 2021

Stations	Cross-Sectional Area (sqm)	Discharge (cumecs)	Million liters per day (MLD)
Station 1 (1 st Feb 2017)	49.04	11.27	973
Station 2 (1 st Feb 2017)	25.63	8.20	708
Station 3 (1 st Feb 2017)	29.06	11.33	978
Station 1 Sept 2017	198	1251.4	108086

Table 7: Water volume at Bairabi station adapted from Lalramchulloa, 2021

At Lunglei, the Tlawng River records its lowest discharge within the dry season (0.865 cumecs) and the highest during the monsoon (8.8 cumecs). At Sairang, the mean discharge is 2.13 cumecs in the lean period, increasing to 17.8 cumecs in the rainy months. In Ailawng, discharge averages 3.3 cumecs in the dry season but surges to 178.8 cumecs during the monsoon. At Bairabi, the flow is 10.3 cumecs in the lean period, rising sharply to 1,251 cumecs in the wet season. Overall, discharge consistently increases in the downstream direction, as reflected in Table 8 & 9 (Figure 3 & 4). Seasonal variations also produce changes both at individual points and along the channel, primarily due to variations in rainfall. The relationship suggests that river discharge is directly proportional to rainfall, with higher precipitation leading to greater flow volumes.

The Tlawng River experienced its most severe flooding in the past fifty years during 2016, 2017, and 2018. From March to September of these years, rainfall levels were significantly higher than in preceding years. As a result, hundreds of houses situated along the riverbanks were inundated and residents had to be relocated (Figure 2). Prolonged rainfall caused widespread destruction across several districts in the study region. The towns of Sairang, Hortoki, and Bairabi were the most severely affected, as their valleys are broader and more level compared to other areas, leading to an expansion of the wetted perimeter during major floods. Additionally, deforestation in the river's catchment for agricultural activities increased surface runoff, which in turn intensified river discharge. Many families lost their homes and belongings due to this abrupt natural disaster.

Stations	Rainfall (in mm)	Discharge (in cumecs)
Bairabi (February 2017)	5.7	10.3
Ailawng (March 2017)	124.4	3.3
Sairang (February 2017)	5.7	2.13
Lunglei (Sept 2018)	121.4	0.865

Table 8: Rainfall discharge comparison during lean Season adapted from Lalramchulloa, 2021

Figure 2: Heavy rainfall causing flood in Sairang in the year 2017 (Lalramchulloa, 2021)

Figure 3: Discharge and Rainfall relationship in lean Season (Lalramchulloa, 2021)

Stations	Rainfall (in mm)	Discharge (in cumecs)
Lunglei (July 2018)	363.4	8.8
Ailawng (Sept 2017)	344.7	178.8
Sairang (Aug 2017)	441	17.8
Bairabi(Sept 2017)	344.7	1251

Table 9: Discharge and Rainfall relationship in rainy season adapted from Lalramchulloa, 2021

Figure 4: Rainfall discharge relationship during rainy season adapted from Lalramchulloa, 2021

Year/Month	Rainfall	Discharge (MLD)
March 2010	102.5	144.8
April 2010	191.3	224.64
Feb 2011	1.3	195.06
March 2011	54.7	174
Feb 2012	15.4	104.9
March 2013	3.6	126.04

Table 10: Rainfall- discharge assessment at PHE site Dihmunzawl adapted from PHE Department, 2015

Figure 5: Rainfall in milimeter and discharge and in cumecs- assessment at PHE site, Dihmunzawl adapted from Lalramchulloa, 2021

The data thus presented (Table 10) indicated that the discharge of the Tlawng River rises with increasing rainfall both at specific points and along its course. As additional tributaries join the main channel, the volume of flow also grows in the downstream direction. Even under limited rainfall conditions, sites with a wider cross-sectional area and higher flow velocity record greater discharge compared to locations receiving more rainfall but characterized by lower velocity and smaller cross-sections (Table 11) (Figure 6). In general, when velocity remains constant, a larger cross-sectional area corresponds to a higher river discharge.

Stations	Cross- sectional area (in sqm)	Rainfall (in mm)	Velocity(mps)	Discharge(cumecs)
Bairabi	34.57	5.7	0.33	10.3
Ailawng	41.89	124.4	0.08	3.3
Sairang	19.65	5.7	0.1	2.13
Lunglei	22.7	121.4	0.2	0.86

Table 11: Hydraulic parameters in lean season adapted from Lalramchulloa, 2021

Figure 6: Association between various hydraulic parameters in lean season adapted from Lalramchulloa, 2021

Stations	Cross-sectional area (sqm)	Rainfall (in mm)	Velocity (mps)	Discharge (in cumecs)
Bairabi(September 2017)	198	344.7	6.32	1251
Sairang (August 2017)	118.7	441	0.5	17.8
Ailawng (September 2017)	127.7	344.7	1.4	178.8
Lunglei (July 2018)	28.27	363.4	0.31	8.8

Table 12: Hydraulic parameters in rainy season adapted from Lalramchulloa, 2021

Figure 7: Association between various hydraulic parameters in rainy season adapted from Lalramchulloa, 2021

Figure 8: Simple Scatter plot with Fit Line showing relationship between Discharge and Rainfall adapted from Lalramchulloa, 2021

Figure 9: Simple Scatter plot with Fit Line showing relationship between Discharge and Velocity adapted from Lalramchulloa, 2021

Figure 10: Simple Scatter plot with Fit Line showing relationship between Discharge and Cross-sectional area in km² adapted from Lalramchulloa, 2021

Bairabi exhibits the most substantial discharge among the studied sites, conveying approximately 1,251 cumecs through a 198 sqm cross-section at a velocity of 6.32 mps. In contrast, despite receiving the highest precipitation (441 mm), Sairang’s outflow remains limited to 17.8 cumecs—a discrepancy of 233% between observed and theoretical discharge, likely driven by upstream regulation, significant infiltration, or temporal measurement offsets. Ailawng occupies an intermediary position, discharging 178.8 cumecs and exhibiting less than 1% deviation from theoretical predictions, indicative of robust measurement accuracy. Lunglei presents the most constrained hydraulics, with a 28.27 sqm cross-section and a low velocity of 0.31 mps, resulting in a modest 8.8 cumecs flow characteristic of gentle gradient (Table 12) (Figure 7).

Statistical analysis (Regression) of rainfall and river velocity against discharge produced an R² value of .664, indicating that these two factors together contribute to about 66% of the variation in river discharge (Figure 8). The combination of rainfall and cross-sectional area yielded an R² of .778, showing that they account for 77% of discharge volume (Figure 9). Similarly, cross-sectional area and river velocity produced an R² value of .776, suggesting that these variables also contribute around 77% to the changes in river discharge (Figure 10) (Table 13).

Variables	River Discharge	R
Rainfall and Cross section		Square value
Velocity and Cross section		778
Rainfall and Velocity		776
		664

Table 13: Relationship between rainfall, velocity, cross section with river discharge adapted from Lalramchulloa, 2021

5. Conclusion

This paper explored the interrelationship between rainfall, discharge, and the morpho-dynamic processes of the Tlawng River in Mizoram. Rainfall not only directly influences discharge but also interacts with key factors such as channel velocity and cross-sectional area, thereby shaping river dynamics. Observations from multiple stations confirmed a positive correlation between rainfall and discharge. Downstream locations recorded greater flow volumes, largely due to wider cross-sections and the cumulative addition of water from tributaries. A clear seasonal contrast was also evident, with discharge levels rising sharply in the monsoon in comparison to the dry season.

The findings further revealed that even in areas receiving relatively low rainfall, the size of the channel and flow velocity remain decisive in determining discharge levels. Broader channels and faster currents produced higher discharge, a conclusion reinforced by regression analysis which showed that rainfall and cross-sectional area together explained about 77% of the variation in river discharge.

The study also drew attention to extreme rainfall years (2016–2018), when the river experienced destructive floods. These events highlighted the vulnerability of riverside settlements and the importance of understanding hydrological behavior for flood preparedness. Additionally, deforestation in the catchment for agricultural expansion has accelerated surface runoff, intensifying flood risks during heavy rainfall periods.

In summary, rainfall, channel velocity, and cross-sectional dimensions collectively exert a strong influence on the hydrodynamics of the Tlawng River. The results provide valuable guidance for flood risk reduction, river basin management, and sustainable land-use planning, while also offering a basis for future hydrological and geomorphological investigations in the region.

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